

Taunting the Tyrant of Antiquity – Isaiah 14:4-21

One of the great yields of the discovery and translation of one million-plus cuneiform tablets from the ancient world is the greater awareness of prophetic ministry throughout the Mediterranean world in every society. Prophecy was not unique to Israel, as the Scriptures themselves testify. One only must think of Balaam, son of Peor, hired by Balak to curse Israel or the pagan prophets of Baal in the Elijah saga. While some have sought to diminish entirely the divide between Hebrew and pagan prophets,¹ more discerning scholars have noted that while similarities exist, the uniqueness of the biblical prophets remains intact. John Walton states,

Certainly there are many similarities of social function and oracular form. Yet certain key differences remain. Non-Israelite prophecy almost entirely lacks three important features: a sense of prophetic call, a challenge to king and people, and an ethical concern. These loom large in Biblical prophecy....²

Drilling down further, one discovers that the biblical prophets not only challenged their people, but they also spoke to other nations. Besides the numerous generic prophecies which speak of God's judgment of or salvation to the nations, five prophets spoke a series of oracles to Israel's neighbors and great world empires. One finds them in Isaiah 13-23, Jeremiah 46-51, Ezekiel 25-32, Amos 1-2, and Zephaniah 2:4-15.³

It is one of Isaiah's oracles that is the theme of this paper. Chapters 13-14 are his words against Babylon, and in 14:4-21, Isaiah expresses himself in words that many call a taunt song. A taunt song is "... a special literary genre that expresses public humiliation and execration over

¹ "The contents of the prophetic books are certainly not unique in the Bible." This quote by Lester Grabbe is quoted by Donald E. Gowan, *Theology of the Prophetic Books*, Westminster Press, Louisville, KY, 1998, p. 3.

² *The NIV Cultural Backgrounds Study Bible*, "Prophets," John H. Walton, Zondervan, Grand Rapids, MI, 2016, 1487.

³ In addition to these series of oracles against nations, one could include Nahum's oracle against Assyria, Habakkuk's against Babylon in 2:4-20, and Obadiah's (the entire book) and Malachi's against Edom in 1:2-5.

the ill-fortune of an individual or group.”⁴ In the Bible, one finds it only in Leviticus 26:36-37a; Micah 2:4; Habakkuk 2:6, and Isaiah’s oracle in 14:4-21.⁵ What is especially noteworthy is that Isaiah’s taunt is against the king of Babylon, a bold move by a man living among the small, oft-defeated and vulnerable people of Judah dwarfed by world empires.

The Target of the Taunt

Not all scholars have viewed Isaiah’s words as referring to the king of Babylon. Stephen L. Cook believes the oracle was originally directed against Sargon II, king of Assyria, Israel’s and Judah’s primary foe during Isaiah’s ministry. He explains that the taunt fits well with events in Sargon’s life and death. Sargon touted himself “king of the universe” and “ruler of [earth’s] four corners.”⁶ Such self-exaltation fits with the description in verses in 14:13-14. Having ascended to the throne in 722 BC, Sargon II led his empire with seemingly never-ending success, until his ignoble defeat in 705 BC in an attack on Tabal in central Anatolia. He was slain in the field of battle and his corpse was dumped into a common grave with other slain warriors. Cook contends that these events fit well with Isaiah’s description in 14:19ff of a rejected branch, covered with the slain, pierced by a sword, a trampled corpse descending to the pit of a common grave.

If one objects to this view and points to the obvious reference to Babylon in 14:4, Cook counters replies:

Sargon applies to himself the very title in his Babylonian inscriptions, and the move fits and reinforces the picture of an egomaniac aspiring to be a universal king. One of Sargon’s most significant imperial triumphs was taking the Babylonian crown for himself

⁴ Mark A. Hassler, “Isaiah 14 and Habakkuk 2: Two Taunt Songs Against the Same Tyrant?,” *The Master’s Seminary Journal*, 26 no 2, Fall 2015, 221.

⁵ *Ibid.*, 222.

⁶ Stephen L. Cook, “Isaiah 14: The Birth of a Zombie Apocalypse?,” *Interpretation: A Journal of Bible and Theology*, 73 no 2, April 2019, 137.

after ousting Merodach-baladan from the throne in 710 BCE. Sargon spent the next three years residing in Babylon, receiving homage and gifts from distant kingdoms.⁷

Cook believes that a redactor applied the original Sargon taunt to Babylon,⁸ and Prinsloo says, "... this prose framework represents an exilic or post-exilic interpretation of the fact that the fall of Babylon had been accomplished by Yahweh who triumphs over every power in heaven and on earth."⁹

While conservative scholars might balk at this background to Isaiah 14, it does hold merit. It was not uncommon for biblical writers to recast older oracles within new frameworks. Jesus did this! In Matthew 11:23, as opposition mounted against him, Jesus rebuked the cities of Chorazin, Bethsaida, and Capernaum for their unbelief. Jesus used the terminology of Isaiah 14:13-15 to describe Capernaum, "And you, Capernaum, will not be exalted to heaven, will you? You will descend to Hades." This does not mean that Jesus viewed the Isaiah passage as a prophecy. Rather he was using familiar terminology about an ancient king's fate to describe a village's fate. Blomberg clarifies this.

Given that Jesus employs no introductory formula and that he uses the language as a rhetorical question followed by its answer rather than as a pair of predictions as in Isaiah, it is perhaps better to see Jesus using deliberately allusive language in his condemnation of the three cities of his day that would make the astute listener think of Isaiah's similar judgment of notorious OT towns.¹⁰

⁷ Ibid., 133.

⁸ Ibid., 136.

⁹ W.S. Prinsloo, "Isaiah 14:12-15 – Humiliation, Hubris, Humiliation," *Zeitschrift für die alttestamentliche Wissenschaft*, 93 no 3, 1981, 437.

¹⁰ G.K. Beale and D.A. Carson, editors, *Commentary on the New Testament Use of the Old Testament*, "Matthew," Craig L. Blomberg, Baker Academic, Grand Rapids, MI, 2007, 38.

Regardless of the target of the original taunt, the point remains, in an act of faith Isaiah is taunting a monarch of an ancient empire contrasting his self-exaltation with his shameful death and descent to the underworld.

A Closer Look at Isaiah's Taunt

It is time to take a closer look at the pericope. The taunt-song divides into two sections 4b-11 and 12-23 demarcated by the word כִּי־כֵן , translated in the NASB and the NIV with the word “how.”¹¹ In verse 4 one reads, “How the oppressor has come to an end,” and in verse 12 one reads, “How you have fallen from heaven.”

In 4b-11 one finds these descriptions of the oppressor's end.

- 5-6 – The staff/scepter which the tyrant used to strike people and subdue nations is broken by the Lord.
- 7-8 – On earth, the people of the world experience quiet and rest. Then, they break into songs of joy over the tyrant's fall. Isaiah personifies cypress trees and cedars of Lebanon singing. No longer are they cut down by the tyrant.
- 9-11- In the underworld, the spirits of previously fallen kings rise to meet the tyrant as he descends to their abode. They declare how he has become weak as they are and how he has traded the pomp of his palace for a bed and blanket of maggots and worms.

In 12-23 one finds these descriptions of how he has fallen from heaven.

- 12-15 - The one with the glorious titles, shining splendor, and deity-aspiring ambitions is cut down to earth and thrust into Sheol.
- 16-17 – Observers¹² look in wonder at this man who so exalted himself, yet who is now humbled.
- 18-21 – Isaiah contrasts the glorious burial of ancient kings with the ignoble death of the tyrant.
- 22-23 – The Lord affirms the inevitability of destruction. Halladay comments that the threefold statement, “declares the LORD,” “...appears to be an attempt to

¹¹ William L. Holladay, “Text, Structure, and Irony in the Poem of the Fall of the Tyrant, Isaiah 14,” *The Catholic Biblical Quarterly*, 1991, 635.

¹² Who are these observers in 14:16? Holladay gives four candidates. The verse could refer to the general folk of the upper world in contrast to those beneath, passers-by, witnesses of the battle in which Sargon II fell, or the kings in Sheol. Holladay prefers the kings in Sheol. *Ibid.*, 642.

establish the genuineness of the material and the validity of the identification it gives of the realm of the tyrant.”¹³

The Great Reversal

One more major characteristic of this taunt-song must be identified – the theme of the great reversal. Cook, attributing this insight to Christopher Hays, lists the following reversals of fortune for the tyrant.¹⁴

The Reversal	The Text
Instead of professional mourners wailing his death in a state funeral, people rejoice	All the lands are at rest and at peace; they break into singing. Even the junipers and the cedars of Lebanon gloat over you. 14:7-8a
Instead of orations lauding the king’s fecundity, there is relief that deforestation has ceased.	Now that you have been laid low, no one comes to cut us down, 14:8b. The man who made the world a wilderness. 17a
Instead of an extravagant internment in a royal tomb, the tyrant is disgraced in his death.	All the kings of the nations lie in state, each in his own tomb. But you are cast out of your tomb like a rejected branch; you are covered with the slain, with those pierced by the sword, those who descend to the stones of the pit. Like a corpse trampled underfoot, you will not join them in burial. 14:18-20a
Instead of former kings welcoming and lauding him as he descends to the netherworld, they shame and degrade him.	The realm of the dead below is all astir to meet you at your coming; it rouses the spirits of the departed to greet you—all those who were leaders in the world; it makes them rise from their thrones—all those who were kings over the nations. They will all respond, they will say to you, “You also have become weak, as we are; you have become like us.” All your pomp has been brought down to the grave, along with the noise of your harps; maggots are spread out beneath you and worms cover you. 14:9-11
Instead of a royal estate in the netherworld, he is given a place of squalor.	Maggots are spread out beneath you and worms cover you. 14:11

¹³ Ibid., 635.

¹⁴ Cook, 136, 140.

Instead of descendants who remember his name, thus guaranteeing his status in the afterlife, his descendants are cut off which jeopardizes his eternal fate.	Let the offspring of the wicked never be mentioned again. Prepare a place to slaughter his children for the sins of their ancestors; they are not to rise to inherit the land and cover the earth with their cities. 14:20b-21
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What words! What poetry! What a reversal! What a taunt! But most importantly, what an act of faith for Isaiah to write from his beleaguered, humanly weak state of Judah to the ruler of the world. As one looks at everything from Isaiah's poetry to his faith, one with any kind of intellectual prowess and spiritual sensitivity must desire to emulate his creative expression and his faith-filled perspective on human events. Indeed, is this not another reason it was written, not only for the people of Isaiah's day but also for succeeding generations which deal with fresh uprisings of blasphemy and tyranny from new dark lords? If Cook is right that the words were originally about Sargon II, one can see clearly how they were applied to Babylon by faith-filled people of another generation. Cook takes another step when he identifies ancient kings in their graves in Ezekiel 32 greeting fallen Egypt and the tyrant Gog of Ezekiel 38-39 as reuses of Isaiah 14.¹⁵ And, this paper has noted Jesus' re-use of it in Matthew 11 to refer to the pride of his people who refused his message. How, then, could this passage serve the people of the 21st century?

But I Thought This was About Satan!

With so many biblical examples, one must pause and wonder why commentators have identified this passage as a reference to a pre-human rebellion and fall of Satan, or Lucifer, from his place in heaven. One can take, for example, the teaching of Lewis Sperry Chafer, one of the founders of Dallas Theological Seminary.

The crime of Satan is concisely stated in the fourteenth verse as being a purpose in his heart to become *like* the Most High....It was a purpose in his heart which would require

¹⁵ Ibid., 136-141.

the time of the ages wholly to destroy. There could be but one Most High, and the purpose of Satan to become like Him could, naturally, be nothing less than an attempt to dethrone the Almighty. Satan was the first being to manifest a will opposed to the will of God. In the above passage from Isaiah five “I wills” are recorded of him.”¹⁶

Chafer makes no mention in his commentary about human tyrants. It is all about Satan.

Where did Chafer, the esteemed founder of an esteemed seminary get such an idea? To ask it another way, why do so many today believe these verses are about Satan? John Walton has identified the source of this misreading of the text.

The earliest appearance of this association can be found in the writings of Origen. Satan’s fall had been discussed earlier by Tertullian and Justin Martyr but with no obvious references to Isaiah 14.... Jewish writings (cf. 2 Enoch 29:4-5) contained stories of the fall of Satan, but there is no evidence that Isaiah 14 was ever interpreted in relation to that fall.

The doctrine of his fall and its association with Isaiah 14 passed into the mainstream of Christian theology through *Moralia* 34 by Pope Gregory the Great in the seventh century. Once it was part of popular belief, it easily passed into the great pieces of literature, such as Milton’s *Paradise Lost*, which sustained its place in theology. The doctrine was additionally solidified by the way Isaiah 14 was handled in translation. Jerome, interpreting the difficult Hebrew term *helel* in Isaiah 14:12 (NIV “morning star”) as a reference to Venus, used a Latin term for Venus, *Luciferos*, to translate it. As the interpretation of the passage as a reference to Satan became popularized in the centuries following, “Lucifer” was adopted as a variant name for Satan – but only because that was what Satan was called in this passage.

By the sixteenth and seventeenth centuries, when the major English translations were being produced the interpretation was so ingrained that “Lucifer” was retained, even in the King James Version, thus reinforcing to the lay English reader the belief that the passage explicitly concerned Satan.¹⁷

Isaiah’s Mythic Background

If the passage is not talking about Satan, why would Isaiah use such language – ascending to the heavens, becoming like the Most High, falling from heaven – to describe a

¹⁶ Lewis Sperry Chafer, *Satan*, Dunham Publishing, Findlay, OH, 1919, 12.

¹⁷ John H. Walton, *Old Testament Theology*, IVP Academic, Downers Grove, IL, 2017, 201-202.

human ruler? The answer that current scholars are providing is that Isaiah is referencing a well-known myth (or myths) and using it to illustrate the hubris of an earthly king. McKay lists several possibilities of the mythic background to Isaiah's words. He believes it to have a Canaanite-Israelite setting.¹⁸ Some have identified Helel (Star of the Morning) and Shahaar (the Dawn) with different aspects of the moon, the sun, Jupiter, or Venus.¹⁹

A more compelling background identification has come from the research of John Poirier. He notes that scholars have often stumbled upon the fact that no one has yet to find a myth that fits all the phrases of 14:12-15. One myth seems to match verse 12 and another myth verses 13-15. Poirier has concluded that Isaiah is referring to more than one myth. He believes verse 12 to speak of the Phaethon myth and verses 13-15 to speak of well-known and widely spread ideas of coup-of-heaven myths. Isaiah ties them together because both demonstrate the tyrant's hubris.

In the Phaethon myth, Phaeton, son of Helios, wants to establish his divine heritage. He desires to drive Helios' chariot through the skies. Helios sternly warns his son against this but allows his request to prevail. The result was tragic. Phaeton was unable to control the chariot. His request was to mount the skies, but he fell to earth, bringing destruction. Poirier notes several accounts of this myth in antiquity and that it was a popular lamentation and morality story on the danger of pride.²⁰

¹⁸ J.W. McKay, "Helel and the Dawn Goddess," *Vetus Testamentum*, 20 no 4, October 1970, 451-452.

¹⁹ *Ibid.*, 452-453.

²⁰ John C. Poirier, "An Illuminating Parallel to Isaiah 14:12," *Vetus Testamentum*, 49 no 3, July 1999, 378.

Coup-of-heaven myths were prominent with warfare among the gods being a common theme.²¹ He notes how the “mount of the assembly” and the specific reference to Mount Zaphon (v. 13) coincide with the ancient belief that the gods dwelt on mountains where they assembled to decide the affairs of humanity. Zaphon was a mountain in Syria and the abode of Baal.

After promoting these myths as the driving force for 14:12-15, Poirier concludes:

[T]he Babylonian king’s visions of solar grandeur are but the pretensions of a puerile young boy whose talk is cheap and whose actions are costly, we can also appreciate the placement of the most archetypal of all laments within the larger unit of Isa xiv 4b-21 – a unit which several scholars have identified as a mock lament.²²

Conclusion

One discovers in Isaiah 14:4b-23 a remarkable piece of ancient poetry penned by Isaiah. He was a prophet of God and a man of faith who declared the downfall of a prideful pagan king exalting himself as a god. But his boasts would end in destruction. He would fail, and he would fall. He would descend, like all others to the netherworld, and unlike many others, his descent to the abode of the dead would be a descent from a shameful earthly death into eternal shame.

The taunt-song of Isaiah built the faith of his people, became the fertile ground for future words of warning to others exhibiting such pride, and stands today as a warning to all forms of pride and as a template for messages that God’s people must courageously bring to a world where tyranny continues to raise its boastful head.

²¹ Walton, 78-80.

²² Poirier, 386.

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